

THE METHOD OF IMPROVING THE QUASI-PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF THE FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHER BASED ON SCIENTIFIC CIRCLES

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Abstract: The article describes the activities of the "Quasi-professional activity" circle and its role in the formation of professional characteristics of students. The role of quasi-professional activities in the step-by-step professional training of future biology teachers is shown. Consideration of these tasks is explained by the author's belief that the quasi-professional model of education can be fully implemented not only in classrooms, but also in other practice-oriented educational areas of higher education.

Keywords: *quasi-professional activities, modeling, become a "Sensei Statue Owner!" project, design technologies, problem-based learning technology.*

The main task of educational institutions is the harmonious development of a person in all aspects. Today, reforms in the field of education implemented in the Republic, teaching theory of pedagogy and its connection with practice occupy an important place in the formation of professional characteristics of future specialists. Improving the quasi-professional activity of the future teacher is of great importance. Quasi-professional activity is one of the forms of contextual education, which involves modeling a certain segment of professional activity, creating real pedagogical situations [1]. The activities of the "Quasi-professional activity" circle and its role in the formation of professional characteristics of students are described below. By forming a quasi-professional activity in the circle, students learn to solve various professional problems and establish a system of pedagogical interactions, independently solve various problem situations. In addition, this type of activity can be considered as a kind of transitional period between educational activity and educational and professional activity. This increases the level of preparation of students for teaching practice and solves the problem of fear of expressing one's opinion in public, showing professional knowledge [2]. The circle conducts its activities in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the

"National Program of Personnel Training" and the "Regulation on the Search, Identification and Targeted Training of Talented Students" of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education and the legal and regulatory documents developed by Bukhara State University work based on. In the "Preparation of students for quasi-professional activities on the basis of design technologies" class, students are required to organize classes based on design technology, to develop skills related to the essence of this method and its application. Become a 'Sensei Statue Owner' below!" there is talk about the project named. Become a 'Sensei Figurine' Owner!" The event project will be announced by the teacher on Monday of the week. Depending on the completion of tasks indicated next to 10 colored coins, during the week each student will have his own account number, i.e. several coins. In this presentation, the student who collected the most coins will be the owner of the figurine, and the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd place winners will be determined. Candidates for awards will be selected for 6 more stars.

About the assignments:

1) For the wise. Completing complex tasks prepared for gifted students will be credited with coins. It is up to the students to complete these tasks.

2) For parents. Coins will be added to the accounts of parents based on their participation in classes, parent meetings, and on a single electronic education platform for teachers, students, parents, administrators of educational institutions, and representatives of educational management bodies.

3) For active participation in classes and textbooks. In addition to students' active participation in classes, coins are also added to their accounts for always having their tools ready.

4) For creative work. In this case, coins will be thrown for students to prepare independent educational tasks such as crosswords, tests, videos, thematic abstracts, various mock-ups and mock-ups.

5) For the "Sensei figurine" lesson. On one day of the week, reinforcement topics are selected from any subject. Coins collected in this lesson will be credited to the student's account.

6) For duty. Coins are tossed based on the supervision of the students on duty.

7) For behavior. Coins that the most polite children will have. These coins can also be used to determine the level of achievement of the educational goals of each subject.

8) For being able to express his independent opinion. In this case, coins are thrown for the efforts made to form a culture of communication during

the tasks of problem-based educational technologies and didactic game technologies used in classes.

9) Fine. Coins are awarded for late students, missed class hours, disorderly conduct in class. In this case, 2 of the previously collected coins are removed. When the defect is corrected, it will be returned again.

10) Bankruptcy. Coins for unexcused absences, unexcused absences. All coins collected by the student will be removed.

This project activates students' participation in collective work, serves as a good tool for connecting parents with the school. It eases the supervision of teachers, helps them to achieve high efficiency in the educational process, in other words, helps to create the teacher's class management activity. Another advantage of the "Sensei figurine" is that it is possible to organize classes, contests, events even by dividing students into groups. When dividing into groups, the cognitive potential of students is taken into account. However, the reason for this grouping is not mentioned in order not to dampen the enthusiasm of the students to study. Students can be grouped as follows:

The most active students to group 1;

Group 2 includes students who master education well;

Group 3 includes students who are learning freely;

Group 4 includes students who are not responsible for education;

Group 5 is grouped in the form of students with low learning ability.

By creating tasks suitable for lessons, contests, and events for each of these groups, and by creating an opportunity for students in groups 3-4-5 to participate, the concept "So, I can also compete" and "I can be a winner" will appear in them, and self-confidence is awakened, desire for school, assessment of one's work, analysis, self-control are formed. Among the students are children of low-income families, children under the care of relatives, children of orphanages. They will have limited access to parent coins. This seriously damages their morale. In order to prevent this, "For gifts" coins are used. On Monday, the teacher will announce the conditions to get "For the Smart" coins. These conditions may include: Practical projects: this will focus on the social interests of the project participants or an external client. In this case, the product is predetermined and used in a specific activity [3]. Research projects: this project is structured like a real scientific research, based on the relevance of the chosen topic, defines the research objectives, necessarily advances the hypothesis with confirmation and discusses the obtained results. Informative project: in which the student analyzes an object, event, summarizes and gathers information to present

to a wider audience. Creative projects: where the student takes into account a free and unconventional approach to the presentation of project results. These can be theatrical performances, sports games, visual or decorative works of art, video films [4]. Role projects: In these projects, the structure is not defined and the work is open until completion. Project participants perform specific roles. According to the roles, their tasks are determined. According to the plot of the game, they should perform roles, in appropriate cases, enter into communication as an "official", and mobilize their existing abilities and talents, acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications. In order to achieve the desired result in the process of solving the project, they need to work hard, search, think independently and creatively, independence and consciousness. There is creative exploration here, but role-play projects are considered because the project is solved by students taking on certain roles [5]. Group projects are of great importance in the formation of students' basic competencies: they develop the ability to work with a team, analyze the situation, and make decisions. From experience, it is worth noting that the most difficult process is the organization of the initial stage of work on the project. Sometimes choosing a topic is simply difficult: because it is necessary to take into account the interests of students, the relevance of the issue. Let's say the topic is defined [6-8]. Now it is necessary to distribute the roles in the group: the student who collects theoretical materials, analyzes them, prepares a literature review on the topic is selected. Together with other students, it is necessary to carry out the practical part of the research, that is, to conduct experiments to describe the material under analysis, to take photos or video films, and similar complex processes. Later, active preparations for the presentation of the research project in the republic and then at the regional conference begin. A report is prepared, as a rule, all members of the educational institution or students participate in its preparation. The main author of the research paper presents the project in the traditional way, and then the presentation is discussed and its shortcomings are considered and corrected. The main purpose of pre-listening to the presentation is to form the student to be able to answer them without difficulty even when unexpected and thoughtful questions are asked. Students will work together to make a plan to answer all the questions. Why should research be discussed in advance? The truth is that students feel anxious when defending a project publicly. As a result, there are cases of excitement, inability to concentrate, and inability to express one's thoughts in front of observers. During the initial listening process, the student gathers

the experience of behaving in front of the audience, learns to answer questions correctly, in a word, has the experience of giving a speech and holding a discussion.

It is desirable to organize students' research work in the following directions:

a) preparation of practical and laboratory work, seminar classes. For example, interesting projects on the life and work of great scientists are prepared (A.M. Butlerov, A. Nobel, K. Linney). Projects devoted to the history of scientific discovery, the history of the use of everyday objects (matches) or products (chocolate) become real research projects.

b) by participating in competitions, festivals, conferences, students' research activities are developed outside the classroom [9].

Exemplary cases are selected to receive coins "for active participation in classes and textbooks". But even a casual learner would like to have such a coin. In such cases, it is suggested to compete with students in one's own group. Even a small achievement of the student is encouraged: "Hey, you answered better today than yesterday", "You did this exercise more accurately than the last one, so you have a coin for active participation in classes and tutorials." Students should complete the following tasks in order to collect coins "for creative work" in their accounts:

"With my own hands"

In this, students prepare forms and models from various objects related to their chosen topic, and these models are put on the exhibition called "With my own hands" in the classroom.

"My impressions"

In this case, students are required to go to production enterprises with their parents or to meet famous people, to participate in the festive events of our people, to travel to the heart of nature. They express their impressions through photos, drawings, statements and essays, and prepare them in file folders or ordinary notebooks. These notebooks will be exhibited at the "My Impressions" exhibition.

"My Book" and "My Dictionary"

In this, students prepare booklets with their own hands, bring samples of their creations to it, decorate with pictures, collect samples of folklore. In the book called "My Dictionary", students write down the explanations of the terms they do not understand from any subject. It is very useful in mastering subjects. These books are included in the exhibition "My book".

"I am a little scientist"

In this, students describe their mini-research. For example: Information about Karl Berg is collected from other books, newspapers, magazines and through internet networks. These data are recorded in photographs, they describe small scientific works. Parents also help in this work. And the student will have coins both for creative work and for his parents. So, in one month, 4 exhibitions will be created by students in the classroom.

"My plant or animal"

A living corner is created in the classroom to teach students how to grow and reproduce houseplants and animals. The teacher distributes plant seeds to the students and gives them the task of collecting them. Students are allowed to take care of any animals they want. One condition is announced during the week to get "For Duty" coins, and the students will be observed on duty - cleanliness of their desks, sabbaticals, participation in public insects and taking care of flowers in the classroom - and the result will be seen on Saturday and they will get duty coins.

Students receive coins "for behavior" not for always orderly situations, but for exemplary behavior. For example: they get these coins for returning lost money to the owner, eliminating sick friends, helping the elderly. In order to receive coins "for being able to express an independent opinion", students should constantly follow the following directions in the process of education and training in order to improve their speech:

able to express one's opinion independently and freely;

perfect knowledge of the laws and norms of the Uzbek literary language;

regular self-control and speech activity;

continuous development of his speech culture;

that the communicator creates the conditions for mastering the rules of literary speech in all cases [10].

"Penalty coins" are issued for students who are late to class, leave textbooks at home, and for minor infractions. In such cases, the 2 coins previously received by students will be withdrawn. Only if the defect is rectified will the penalty be charged and the previous coins returned. If the fine is not corrected within a week, one more fine will be issued and postponed until the next week. In order for the student to correct the fine, an explanatory letter is written in the diary and the parent is signed at the end of the letter. Only then will the penalty coin be removed. Bankruptcy Coins are awarded for truancy, 3 consecutive fines, gross misconduct. All coins previously received by the student will be withdrawn, and only half of the coins will be returned if the errors are corrected. In order to correct

mistakes, an assignment is given, taking into account the potential of the student, and an explanatory letter is written in the notebook of the student's diary. The opinion of the parents must also be recorded in this letter. If the parent gives an opinion in cases of fines and bankruptcy, the student's account will receive a coin for the parent. With this, the student quickly overcomes his shortcomings and approaches his work with enthusiasm. When making coins, special attention should be paid to their color. Coins of 10 different colors are selected in 10 conditions, and a sample of the selected color coin is placed next to each condition. In this way, the student will know what coin he will get if he fulfills the condition, and the teacher will also know how easily the student fulfills the condition. Shiny gold coins are the pick of the discerning. The shine of these coins attracts the child's attention and he will definitely try to do this trick. Shiny silver coins are the choice for parents. Red, yellow, green - similar simple colors are selected according to other conditions. However, it is better to choose a brown color for a fine, and a black color for bankruptcy. Coins of each color (from 30, 40 and 50) are good to have in the bank vault. There are 10 pockets at the bottom of the treasure display, and each pocket contains 10 coins of different colors. As an honorary prize winner, the student who holds the Sensei statuette will have a picture of the shiny statuette affixed to his pocket and a picture of the same statuette will be affixed to his diary. A contest with several sensei statue veterans can also be held later. Most importantly, talented students in the class are identified and additional practical training is conducted with them. These students are announced as Junior Olympiad candidates, and Olympiads are held in the classroom at the end of each quarter. Parents are invited to the event, that is, to the presentation, and medallions are given to Olympiad participants for 1st, 2nd, 3rd place, and the statue of sensei is ceremoniously put on the winner of the highest place. As mentioned above, this project can also be used in the classroom. For this purpose, any topic from any subject is chosen once a week and announced to the students as "Sensei statue lesson". Become a 'Sensei Figurine' Owner!" After it is explained to the members of the circle based on the project, we will apply it among them as well. Because it requires a great pedagogical ability from the future teacher to properly organize the project. This, in turn, requires the development of quasi-professional activities. Students are given the following assignments: Students can earn "For Duty" and "For Conduct" coins by participating in or organizing community affairs, demonstrating their leadership skills. Students should develop a communication culture in order

to be able to express their independent opinion. For this purpose, in the process of preparing and rehearsing a speech for communication, students should independently find answers to the following questions:

1) What kind of thought do I want to evoke in the audience?

2) What kind of mood do I want to create a positive atmosphere in the audience?

3) What kind of intonation and rhythm does the content and context of the speech require?

Students should record their speech several times (audiorecorder, dictaphone) and try to correct their mistakes and rehearse their speech before any educational activity. They are required to enrich their speech with colorful artistic and literary words. They should form skills such as enriching and filling their impressions, attracting the attention of students with the perfection, purity, and effectiveness of the teacher's speech, finding a way to their hearts, and eliminating all conflicts encountered in professional pedagogical activity without any difficulty [13, 14]. "Penalty" coins are given to students who come late to classes and do not complete assignments, and "bankruptcy" coins are given to students who have very serious deficiencies. On the basis of the above tasks, students will learn about their shortcomings based on the coins they have accumulated in their accounts during the week, and the teacher will give them additional information and tasks to correct these mistakes.

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